

MECHANICS OF KINKING IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Kink band formation is a dominant compressive failure mechanism in unidirectional fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRPCs). This paper synthesizes two studies conducted to look at kink band formation at the micro and meso scales within a composite. The first study captures kink band evolution through a variational energy approach applied to a single fiber–matrix unit cell, revealing the influence of matrix nonlinearity and imperfection sensitivity. In contrast, the second study employs high-fidelity finite element micromechanics simulations to investigate compressive failure in 0° plies under multiaxial loading and mesoscale/microscale fiber misalignment. Together, these works elucidate how microstructural mechanics and boundary conditions govern kink initiation, strength variability, and post-peak response in composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRPCs) have become indispensable in modern aerospace, marine, and defense applications due to their superior stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios. Among these, unidirectional carbon fiber composites with 0° fiber orientations are particularly valued for their axial load-carrying capacity. However, under compressive loading, these materials are susceptible to a distinctive failure mechanism known as kink band formation.

Publication by Allix et al. [1] provides a comprehensive review of kinking failure, and this, along with the summaries by Schultheisz and Waas [2,3], outlines the current state of the art in modeling kink band formation in fiber composites. Broadly, models proposed for kink band formation can be categorized into three groups: micro-buckling models, kinking models, and bending theories. The micro-buckling model was first introduced by Rosen [5], who equated the compressive strength of a composite to the buckling strength of a perfectly straight, elastic fiber–matrix system. However, these models do not account for fiber misalignment or matrix nonlinearity and, as a result, significantly overpredict compressive strength.

Argon [4] was the first to identify kinking, rather than micro-buckling, as the dominant failure mechanism in compression. Subsequent models by Budiansky and Fleck [5], Budiansky et al. [6], Fleck et al. [7], Zidek and Vollmecke [8], and Hahn and Williams [9] enhanced Argon's original formulation by incorporating initial fiber misalignment and matrix nonlinearity. While these models advanced the understanding of compressive strength prediction, they did not account for the post-peak compressive response, which is a critical aspect of damage evolution in FRPCs.

To capture post-peak behavior beyond the onset of kinking, bending theory was introduced, wherein finite bending resistance of the fibers is explicitly modeled. Fleck et al. [5] proposed this approach, which was later analyzed in detail by Kyriakides et al. [10], and expanded by Lee and Waas [11], who also included the possibility of fiber–matrix splitting as an additional energy release mechanism. Bending theory has since been applied by several researchers, including Chung and Weitsman [12], De Moraes and Marques [13], and Sun and Wanki Jun [14]. These models generally assume an initial imperfection, be it straight, misaligned, or sinusoidal, leading to the formation of a misaligned band inclined at an angle. The material is typically modeled as a homogeneous anisotropic solid under equilibrium with respect to compressive forces, bending moments, and shear stresses. The corresponding differential equilibrium equations are solved numerically to yield the deformed configuration. These approaches often rely on an elastic–plastic matrix description, with limitations on the accuracy of post-kink predictions.

More recently, Pimenta et al. [15] employed bending theory to derive a closed-form expression for kink strength. Their model introduced a partitioning of the composite into elastic and plastic domains, assuming the matrix to be elastic–perfectly plastic and that the peak load coincides with matrix yielding. Consequently, the pre-peak response mirrors earlier models [12, 13], while the post-peak response is derived from an equilibrium analysis of the two domains. Although their predictions aligned qualitatively with finite element simulations, the latter showed that the actual peak load does not coincide with matrix yield [16]. This discrepancy arises from the assumptions used to define peak load and from the discretization of the elastic and plastic domains.

Computational studies [12-21] exist in the literature to investigate compression-induced kink failure using micromechanical frameworks. A general overview of these methods is available in a recent review by Daum et al. [21].

The present analytical formulation builds upon prior two-dimensional micromechanical frameworks, such as those of Chung and Weitsman [12] and Pimenta et al. [15], which model the bending equilibrium of a single fiber embedded in a nonlinear matrix. However, unlike earlier approaches, the current model does not impose assumptions regarding the onset of kinking strength or its relationship to matrix yielding. Nor does it rely on discretizing the post-kink response into separate elastic and plastic zones. Instead, the model treats the deformation response as a continuous evolution, where elastic and plastic domains emerge naturally from the computed solution.

In addition, this study adopts a systematic, step-by-step approach to investigate kink band formation under transverse loads and varying boundary conditions. The analysis aims to address several critical questions: (1) What is the appropriate size of the unit cell for kink band analysis? (2) How do misalignments, both within and across the unit cell, influence kink band initiation and propagation? (3) How do different transverse boundary conditions affect the compressive strength of a representative unit cell? (4) What is the compressive response of a simple laminate under axial load combined with various transverse boundary conditions?

2 ANALYTICAL MODELING OF KINK BAND FORMATION

A novel analytical approach to describe kink banding in unidirectional fiber composites is proposed, and reported in Davidson and Waas [18]. This formulation is based on a single fiber–matrix unit cell subjected to axial compression, where the fiber geometry included a predefined imperfection represented as a sinusoidal waviness. The fiber was modeled as an Euler–Bernoulli beam, while the surrounding matrix was treated as a nonlinear shear material characterized by an odd-order polynomial response (figure 1). The analysis was carried out under the plane strain assumption, which is valid for high fiber volume fractions and narrow band geometries.

Figure1. Analytical micromechanics model

The total potential energy of the system was expressed as a combination of fiber axial and bending energy, matrix shear energy, and external work. The primary unknowns were the transverse deflection of the fiber and its axial displacement, both of which were approximated using parameterized functions to allow for energy minimization. Importantly, the model did not require any pre-assumed criteria for matrix yield or kink onset; instead, it allowed these phenomena to emerge naturally from the energy minimization process.

The analysis revealed that compressive strength does not coincide with the matrix yield point. Rather, matrix yielding initiates the softening behavior, and the actual peak load occurs after a sequence of fiber deformation events including amplitude growth and rotation (figure 2). The model further captured post-peak behavior characterized by a snap-back instability, indicating a sudden loss of load-bearing capacity upon kink band formation. A detailed stability analysis using the second variation of potential energy confirmed that the instability is governed by the interaction of two deformation modes, one dominated by amplitude change and the other by fiber rotation. This dual-mode interaction has not been emphasized in previous analytical models, which often assumed a single critical parameter such as matrix yield or fiber misalignment.

Figure2. Stages of kink band formation.

One of the major strengths of this model lies in its ability to simulate sensitivity to initial imperfections. Parametric studies showed that even small variations in the misalignment angle could lead to significant changes in compressive strength and kink band width. These results aligned well with experimental observations and provided a deeper mechanistic understanding of why kink band widths often exhibit large scatter in composite testing.

3 COMPUTATIONAL MICROMECHANICS UNDER MULTIAXIAL LOADS

The study of kink band formation is further advanced by employing computational micromechanics to simulate compressive behavior under realistic multiaxial loading conditions. This work was motivated by experimental observations of bolted joints in fiber composites, where the presence of transverse bolt loads leads to complex stress states within the laminate. Specifically, the 0° plies adjacent to the bolt experience both axial compression and transverse confinement, which dramatically alter their failure response.

Figure 3. Micro and meso scale misalignment

To capture these effects, a finite element-based micromechanical model was developed. Each 0° ply was explicitly modeled using discrete fibers embedded in a nonlinear matrix, with mesoscale and microscale fiber misalignments incorporated through stochastic distributions. The mesoscale misalignment angle, representing ply-level deviation, was modeled by rotating the unit cell, while microscale fiber waviness was introduced using randomized sinusoidal profiles with varying amplitude and wavelength. The matrix behavior was characterized using experimentally calibrated elastic–plastic laws.

Figure 4. Boundary conditions studied

Several boundary conditions were explored to simulate the effect of different structural constraints, including unconstrained, fixed edge, pressure-loaded, and spring-supported cases. These configurations allowed the authors to evaluate the impact of lateral confinement, which is known to increase compressive strength but also change the failure mode from kink banding to crushing or splitting in some instances.

One of the key outcomes of this study was the identification of usable unit cell aspect ratios that isolate kink band formation without interference from Euler buckling. The simulations demonstrated that when the aspect ratio is too high, global buckling dominates; when it is too low, the kink band formation is artificially constrained. A sweet spot was found where kink bands formed naturally, and boundary effects were minimized. Further, the computational results confirmed that both mesoscale and microscale misalignments significantly influence the strength and stability of the composite. For a given mesoscale misalignment angle, repeated simulations with different microscale realizations within a stack-up produced a range of strength values, capturing the scatter typically observed in experiments (figure 5).

Figure 5. Compression behavior variation depending on location of zero plies with a stackup.

The results also emphasized that kink band formation can occur even in the absence of mesoscale misalignment, driven solely by fiber-to-fiber microscale imperfections. The macroscopic stress–strain curves obtained from the simulations showed classic snap-back behavior, consistent with the analytical predictions from the analytical study. This reinforced the conclusion that kink banding is an imperfection-sensitive, highly localized failure mode governed by the interplay of geometry, material nonlinearity, and boundary constraints.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The two studies together form a cohesive framework for understanding kink band formation in fiber-reinforced composites. The analytical model provides a mechanistic foundation, revealing how fiber curvature and matrix nonlinearity interact to precipitate failure. It demonstrates the importance of capturing both amplitude and rotation in the deformation profile and explains why compressive strength cannot be predicted solely based on matrix yield criteria.

The computational study builds upon these insights by incorporating realistic boundary conditions and stochastic misalignment fields. It reveals how external confinement and ply stacking alter the local stress state, often leading to non-intuitive failure behavior. The agreement between simulation outcomes and experimental observations validates the micromechanical modeling approach and confirms that compressive strength is not a fixed material property but rather a structural response conditioned by multiple parameters.

Together, the studies highlight the need to consider both mesoscale architecture and microscale imperfections when designing composite structures for compressive loads. They also offer a roadmap for future research, suggesting that models should not only predict strength but also capture the evolution of damage and post-peak behavior. In applications such as bolted joints or aerospace panels, where multi-axial stress states are common, these models can be instrumental in predicting localized failures and informing design decisions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Allix O, Feld N, Baranger E, et al. The compressive behaviour of composites including fiber kinking: Modelling across the scales. *Mecc* 2014; 49(11): 2571–2586.
- [2] Schultheisz, CR, and Waas, AM. Compressive failure of composites, part I: Testing and micromechanical theories. *Prog Aerosp Sci* 1996; 32(1): 1–42.
- [3] Schultheisz, CR, and Waas, AM. Compressive failure of composites, part II: Experimental studies. *Prog Aerosp Sci* 1996; 32(1): 43–78.
- [4] Argon AS. *Fracture of composites (Treatise on Materials Science and Technology)*. New York, NY: Academic Press, 1972.
- [5] Budiansky, B, and Fleck, NA. Compressive failure of fibre composites. *J Mech Phys Solids* 1993; 41(1): 183–211.
- [6] Budiansky, B, Fleck, NA, and Amazigo, JC. On kink-band propagation in fiber composites. *J Mech Phys Solids* 1998; 46(9):1637–1653.
- [7] Fleck, NA, Deng, L, and Budiansky, B. Prediction of kink width in compressed fiber composites. *J Appl Mech* 1995; 62: 329–337.
- [8] Zidek, RAE, and Vollmecke, C. On the influence of material non-linearities in geometric modeling of kink band instabilities in unidirectional fiber composites. *Int J Non-Lin Mech* 2014; 62: 23–32.
- [9] Hahn, HT, and Williams, JG. Compression failure mechanisms in unidirectional composites. In: *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Seventh Conference)*, 1986, 115–139.
- [10] Kyriakides, S, Arseculeratne, R, Perry, E, et al. On the compressive failure of fiber reinforced composites. *Int J Solids Struct* 1995; 32(6): 689–738.

- [11] Lee, SH, and Waas, A. Compressive response and failure of fiber reinforced unidirectional composites. *Int J Fract* 1999; 100:275–306.
- [12] Chung, I, and Weitsman, Y. A mechanics model for the compressive response of fiber reinforced composites. *Int J Solids Struct* 1994; 31(18): 2519–2536.
- [13] De Morais, AB, and Marques, AT. A micromechanical model for the prediction of the lamina longitudinal compression strength of composite laminates. *J Compos Mater* 1997; 31(14): 1397–1412.
- [14] Sun, C, and Wanki Jun, A. Compressive strength of unidirectional fiber composites with matrix non-linearity. *Compos Sci Tech* 1994; 52(4): 577–587.
- [15] Pimenta, S, Gutkin, R, Pinho, ST, et al. A micromechanical model for kink-band formation, part II: Analytical modelling. *Compos Sci Tech* 2009; 69(7–8): 956–964.
- [16] Pimenta, S, Gutkin, R, Pinho, ST, et al. A micromechanical model for kink-band formation, part I: Experimental study and numerical modelling. *Compos Sci Tech* 2009; 69(7–8): 948–955.
- [17] Lee S, Waas A, Compressive response and failure of fiber reinforced unidirectional composites, *Int J Fracture* 100 (1999) 275–306,
- [18] Davidson P, Waas AM, Mechanics of kinking in fiber-reinforced composites under compressive loading, *Mathematics and Mechanics of Solids*..
- [19] Pimenta S, Gutkin R, Pinho S, Robinson P, A micromechanical model for kink-band formation: Part I - Experimental study and numerical modelling, *Compos Sci Technol* 69 (7–8) (2009) 948–955, ISSN 0266–3538,
- [20] Yuan Y, Yao X, Niu K, Liu B, Wuyun Q. Compressive failure of fiber reinforced polymer composites by imperfection. *Compos Part A: Appl Sci Manuf* 2019;118:106–16.
- [21] Daum B, Feld N, Allix O, Rolfes R. A review of computational modelling approaches to compressive failure in laminates. *Compos Sci Technol* 2019;181:.